

Nature of Time

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1 Abstract

In this paper, we show why time shouldn't be considered as a real property of the universe. With d'Alembert interpretation of Galileo experiments, of balls rolling on an inclined surface, we will see how we have to consider time as a mathematics parameter only. Since time doesn't exist in reality, we explain what is the arrow of time and what is an instant of time. Also a new relativity theory is needed and is presented. The transformation is done in the velocity domain rather than in the space-time domain.

2 Introduction

Through the ages, the nature of what we call "time", has been a great philosophical concern and is at present an essential question for physicists. Nowadays, it is the dream for physicists to unify Quantum Mechanics and Einstein General Relativity theory. Their goal is to get an overall theory to modelize all the phenomena acting in the universe, from infinitely small dimensions to infinitely large, and "time" is a major element for this unification.

This question of the real nature of time is a headache for philosophers and a real nightmare for physicists, and there is no clear answer to that question. A great number of physicists are claiming that time doesn't exist, but it seems to be only a belief without a demonstration of its non-existence, and by what it could be replaced.

However, does "time" really exist? Why do we have the sensation of an "arrow of time", while the equations of physics are reversible with the variable "time"? For example, the article of Dan Romalo (Dan Romalo, 2012)[1] given during the 19th annual Conference of the NPA (Natural Philosophy Alliance), on the meaning of absolute time, concludes that it is not wise to consider time as a fundamental physical entity. His presentation is rather philosophical and unfortunately having made his conclusion, he didn't go through his ideas. Effectively, if time is not a real physical entity, why he didn't ask himself by which entity it could be replaced? This paper pushes us to go further.

Doing a bibliographical study on the subject the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Professor Carlo Rovelli of CNRS (Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique) thinks it is necessary to free ourselves from the notion of time. He indicates the possibility to formulate Newtonian Mechanics, Quantum Mechanics and General Relativity without using temporal parameter. Indeed, Americans Bryce DeWitt and John Wheeler obtained an equation for quantum gravity where time does not appear! This result is obtained by applying the rules of Quantum Mechanics to the General Relativity theory. But Carlo Rovelli says we have to give up time on one side but continues to use Einstein GR on the other side, for which time is a necessity! Since Carlo Rovelli did not question

the General Relativity theory, time has inevitably an existence through the notion of space-time universe.

- * Julian Barbour sees the arrow of time as the pages of a book and although he does not believe in the real existence of time, he cannot give another definition,
- * George Snowdon points out there is maybe a difference between duration of event and time,
- * Julian Barbour, Sandra E baron and Peter Wamai Wanjohi are thinking the notion of time to be coming from the movements of objects in the universe.

To understand the following approach, it is important to see that in our universe everything is moving or is transforming due to physical processes; galaxies, stars, planets, rocks, life, etc. Each one is moving with its own velocity and/or is physically transforming with its own velocity of processing.

3 Acceleration versus velocity

To set in motion a matter body, a force is needed to be applied. We know that a force, when applied to a body, will provide it an acceleration. However, to relate the increase of velocity with respect to the given acceleration is not so obvious. When this subject came up in the 18th century, it gave rise to discussions between great mathematicians like d'Alembert, Euler, Leibnitz, Newton, etc.

It was d'Alembert (1717 - 1783), interpreting Galileo experiments of balls rolling on an inclined surface, who expressed it in the following form, with dt as a "duration of time" (Véronique Le Ru, 1994)[2]:

$$\phi * dt = dv \tag{1}$$

where $\phi * dt$ is "the quantity to which the increase of velocity dv is proportional", ϕ being what we call acceleration.

It is important to stress that here " dt " is not a differential increase of time, like in differential calculation, but only a constant small "duration". Following d'Alembert, the expression $\phi * dt$ must not be separated in elements, since " dt " is a "duration" which is not a real physical quantity, and that we cannot derive velocity v by a non real entity.

For velocity we should have define a metric to measure velocity, in the same way as we do it for space with the meter as a metric. Instead, historically, man defines "time" to measure the "duration" between two events relative to the moving earth, which is a mean to compare velocities.

If we pose $\langle v \rangle$ the mean velocity on an interval dx during the "duration" dt of this event, in the same way as d'Alembert did for the acceleration, we get:

$$\langle v \rangle * dt = dx \tag{2}$$

To get rid of dt we can now divide the two above expressions and obtain:

$$\frac{\phi * dt}{\langle v \rangle * dt} = \frac{dv}{dx} \tag{3}$$

Then acceleration is given by:

$$\phi = \langle v \rangle \frac{dv}{dx} \tag{4}$$

Evidently, for a constant acceleration, we have for $\langle v \rangle$:

$$\langle v \rangle = \frac{v + v + dv}{2} = v + \frac{dv}{2} \tag{5}$$

Then the expression for the acceleration becomes:

$$\phi = v \frac{dv}{dx} + O(dv^2) \quad (6)$$

If we take the expression of the corresponding applied force on a body of mass m , using Newton's second law, $F = m * \phi$, we have:

$$F = mv \frac{dv}{dx} + O(dv^2) \quad (7)$$

If we define dv/dx as the acceleration versus distance, then to change the velocity of a body with an impulse mv we have to apply a force equal to the impulse multiplied by this acceleration.

We can also express this force in term of the energy given to the body of mass m , during the process of acceleration, by the formula:

$$F = \frac{d\frac{1}{2}mv^2}{dx} \quad (8)$$

Then a force exerted along a distance interval dx , is equal to the variation of what is called the "kinetic energy" of the moving body.

Unfortunately, the expression for the acceleration a , which is used in physics nowadays, attributed to L. Euler in 1752, is given as the derivative of the velocity v of the matter body versus time:

$$a = dv/dt \quad (9)$$

It is interesting to show how this expression was established. It comes also from Galileo experiments cited above. He obtained that the position x of the ball obeyed to the law:

$$x = 1/2at^2 \quad (10)$$

with a as the constant acceleration and t the duration of the displacement of the ball to the position x .

Increase in position dx between t and $t+dt$ is given by replacing x by $x+dx$ and t by $t+dt$ in the above formula, and simplify to get:

$$dx = atdt + 1/2adt^2 \quad (11)$$

In order to break free from dt , Leibnitz and Newton decided to divide by dt and to make dt going to zero to obtain:

$$dx/dt = at + O(adt) \quad (12)$$

and then, neglecting the dt contribution, they defined instantaneous velocity as:

$$v = dx/dt \quad (13)$$

and acceleration as the second derivative of x versus time.

It is more physical to consider the acceleration on a matter body to be equal to the variation of its kinetic energy during the process. This is coherent with the observation that all objects in the universe are moving or transforming under a certain processing using energy. It is then obvious that what is real in the universe is not time but velocity (or energy)! What we measure with the notion of "duration" is a way to compare motion (or transformation) of different objects between them. It is untrue to associate "duration" with "time".

4 Arrow of time

Since time does not exist as a real entity in the universe, it is necessary to explain the meaning of what we call the "arrow of time". A good example for this is the case of the broken glass. For some physicists there is a non-null probability in which a broken glass can take its original constitution. This is because in all equations of physics, when we use the variable time, it can go plus or minus.

Taking the case of a glass, making it is the result of a process perfectly defined and there is no way of doing it by chance. It needed to have a qualified personnel, adequate materials, and energy processing. But also when somebody let a glass fall down, since everything in the universe is moving or transforming, when the broken glass is on the floor, all the universe keep moving and there is no way to get back to the state of the universe where it was before the glass falls down. It is certain that even by taking the pieces and with a trained personnel and a new process it will not give the original state and anyway the universe is not in the same state either. There is no chance to go back to the beginning of this situation.

Physicists are saying that it is due to the entropy of the system (the glass), which is rising. In thermodynamic for example, a system is said reversible if temperature of the sources and the system are identical. Then there is no exchange of energy and entropy is stable. If there is non-uniformity of pressure, temperature, density, then there is exchange of energy in the system and entropy is rising. In this case, it is said that the transition is irreversible.

It is clear for the glass being broken that there is an exchange of energy and the entropy is rising. We can say that the "arrow of time" is due to irreversibility of the states of the universe, itself due to exchange of energy. Everything in the universe is moving or changing states by consuming energy. In our daily activities, we are always moving and changing interior states by consuming energy. Energy is pushing us in only one direction. There is no way to go back from one situation to another one. We can move in space from one point to another one and go back as we wanted to do, but doing that we must move and use energy, and the universe has changed too. Nevertheless, even if we stay still, not moving, our body is under transformation by many internal processes that are also using energy. It is now clear that there is no time passing but simply energy consuming and entropy rising, meaning we are always passing from one state to another one, and that process gives the impression of the "arrow of time".

5 Instant of time

If time does not really exist in the universe then what is an instant ("instant of time")? What we call an "instant of time" can be explained by a "configuration of the universe", meaning in this expression, that all entities in the universe are characterized by a position in space. For example, let's say the universe is composed of particles. Every particle in the universe has one and only one position and no two particles can have the same position in space. For a given "configuration of the universe", all the particles are precisely defined in a unique position in space. It is what we can call an "instant" of the universe. Every event occurring in the universe can be related to a configuration of the universe and then to "an instant of time".

It is difficult to know that, for one of a fixed configuration of the universe, the earth is precisely situated with respect to the sun, and the other planets and all the galaxies are precisely situated there and there, etc. Then to avoid this problematic we give a name to a particular configuration in space of the universe. In the past, several calendars have been used. Each one was starting from a time zero defined from special events. For example Romans empire have used the founding of Roma, in Japan it was the accession to the throne of a new ruler [3]. From this starting "configuration", astronomers were able to represent the universe and its evolution from this reference starting point.

To fully understand why the notion of "time" isn't real, we have to think about what we do everyday when we want to go to a meeting. Before taking a car or another means of transportation, we verify if we can be "on time" at the location of the meeting. Doing this, we know that the velocity we get during the

transportation is the important factor. Depending on the value of the velocity, it will take us a certain amount of "time duration" to be at the location at the right "instant of time".

6 New relativity theory

Physicists never thought there can be another transformation between two reference frames, transposing all physical laws from a reference frame to another in motion, could exist. A new relativity theory has been proposed by the Taiwanese Young-Sea Huang a few decades ago [4]. Like Einstein GR theory, it is based on the principle of relativity and the constancy of the speed of light. The reader is encouraged to look in detail at this reference to understand the differences with Einstein theory.

The basic principle of the transformation of Young-Sea Huang relativity theory, transformation from a reference frame to another one with a constant velocity between them, is to do it in the velocity space rather than in a space-time coordinates. This transformation is called the differential Lorentz transformation and is transforming physical quantities instead of space-time coordinates, to make laws of nature form-invariant. It makes transformation of infinitesimal virtual displacements between the two reference frames using the speed of light as a reference constant velocity. The differential Lorentz transformation is just like the Lorentz transformation, but in its differential form. It makes a great difference, since with this differential transformation, simultaneity of events is maintained. As said by the author, time and space are of Newtonian nature.

Since Einstein GR is not valid, gravitation force is still to be explain and the idea of Nicolas Fatio de Duillier was raised from the ashes [5].

7 Conclusion

Until now, no one has been able to explain the nature of "time". This is because the term "time" has no reality in the universe and is just a tool invented by man to compare the evolution of different things between them.

We should have kept d'Alembert definition for the acceleration of a body, and found the delivered force to be the variation of the kinetic energy with the displacement.

Then, what is real in our everyday life is the way everything is moving or transforming with respect to the other entities in the universe.

Since "time" is not real, we have to re envisage what can be the relativity of observations between observers going at different velocities.

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